

THE USE OF REALIA IN TEACHING VOCABULARY IN UZBEK EFL CLASSROOMS

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Abstract:

This study examines the use of realia in teaching vocabulary to Uzbek EFL learners. It explores how real-life objects and authentic materials can help learners acquire, retain, and actively use vocabulary in meaningful and practical contexts. The study highlights practical classroom applications, as well as the pedagogical benefits and challenges of using realia in vocabulary instruction. The findings suggest that integrating realia into language teaching can enhance vocabulary development, increase learner motivation, and promote cultural awareness. As a result, the use of realia can make vocabulary learning more engaging, interactive, and effective for Uzbek EFL learners.

Keywords: realia, vocabulary teaching, EFL learners, authentic materials, language learning, Uzbek classrooms, cultural competence

Introduction. Vocabulary plays a crucial role in foreign language learning. According to Norbert Schmitt, vocabulary knowledge plays an essential role in communication because learners cannot express their ideas effectively without sufficient lexical resources [Schmitt, 2000:2]. Additionally, Scott Thornbury emphasizes that vocabulary learning is often considered the foundation of language proficiency since grammar and communication depend mostly on the knowledge of words [Thornbury, 2002:13]. Thornbury also highlights David Wilkins' well-known idea that vocabulary is essential for conveying meaning in communication [Thornbury, 2002:13].

In addition to vocabulary knowledge, the use of authentic materials is considered an important factor in effective language learning. As noted by Alan Gilmore, authentic materials help learners understand how language functions in real-life communication, since they present examples of language that native speakers use in everyday situations [Gilmore, 2007:98].

Therefore, using real-life objects and authentic materials in the classroom can make vocabulary learning more meaningful and practical. One of the effective ways of implementing authentic materials in language teaching is the use of realia, which allows learners to connect new vocabulary with real-life experiences. This approach can increase students' motivation and help them understand vocabulary more effectively in communicative contexts.

Theoretical framework

Understanding the culture associated with a language plays an important role in the process of foreign language learning, since language use is closely connected with cultural practices [Kilickaya, 2004:2]. It supports the development of communicative competence by linking classroom activities with real-life social interactions and cultural norms, which is essential for effective language acquisition. According to Alan Gilmore, authentic materials allow learners to experience natural language use while also helping them become familiar with the cultural dimensions of communication [Gilmore, 2007:100]. This exposure helps bridge the gap between theoretical learning and practical language use, making lessons more engaging and meaningful.

Kilickaya estimates authentic material as a bridge which can connect classroom language learning with real world language use [Kilickaya, 2004:3]. By integrating authentic materials, students have the opportunity to interact with language in contexts that mirror real-life situations. Realia can include objects, texts, or media from the target culture, offering tangible ways to reinforce vocabulary and structures learned in the classroom.

Realia in Vocabulary Teaching

Thornbury defines realia as tangible, real-world objects that teachers use in the classroom to help students understand vocabulary and make learning more concrete [Thornbury, 2002:75]. Realia enables learners to connect words with real objects, making abstract concepts easier to understand and remember. Using real objects in the classroom helps learners link new vocabulary with visual and hands-on experiences, making them effective tools for presenting meaning and supporting memory and comprehension [Thornbury, 2002:7 8]. Incorporating hands-on experiences engages multiple senses, reinforcing both short-term and long-term vocabulary retention and helping learners understand how words are applied in real-life contexts.

According to Schmitt, learners retain vocabulary more effectively when they engage with meaningful contexts instead of studying isolated word lists [Schmitt, 2000:7]. Contextualized vocabulary learning gives words practical meaning, improving recall and enabling learners to use new terms appropriately in real situations.

Application in Uzbek EFL Classrooms

In the context of teaching English to Uzbek EFL students, vocabulary acquisition can be challenging due to limited exposure to English outside the classroom. Realia, or authentic materials, can help bridge this gap by connecting new vocabulary to students' everyday experiences. Teachers can introduce objects, texts, or media that students encounter in their daily lives, such as local food packaging, classroom tools, clothing, or culturally significant items. Using these tangible materials allows learners to visualize and physically interact with words, making vocabulary learning more concrete and memorable. Classroom activities may include handling objects, discussing their uses, role-playing real-life scenarios, or creating presentations based on real items, which encourages active participation and engagement.

Thornbury emphasizes that realia can connect vocabulary learning with students' everyday experiences, helping learners understand words in practical contexts [Thornbury, 2002:96,78]. Gilmore points out that teachers can use real-life objects to make lessons meaningful and engaging, while also introducing cultural elements that enhance understanding [Gilmore, 2007:106,100]. Schmitt highlights that vocabulary retention improves when learners interact with meaningful input and contextualized examples, rather than isolated word lists [Schmitt, 2000:7,9].

By combining practical applications with these scholarly insights, Uzbek EFL teachers can create lessons where vocabulary is not only learned but also applied in real-life contexts. This approach fosters both linguistic competence and cultural awareness, making learning more effective and enjoyable for students.

Advantages and Challenges

Peacock counts a plenty of advantages of using realia in classrooms and the main one is that authentic materials and realia have a significant impact on learner motivation, as students perceive that they are learning language used in real-life situations outside the classroom

[Peacock, 1997:145,148]. This hands-on approach helps Uzbek EFL students see the practical relevance of what they are learning, which fosters long-term retention and a positive attitude toward language learning.

However, using authentic materials can also present challenges. According to Alan Gilmore, one of these difficulties is that complex vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, and unfamiliar cultural references may sometimes be difficult for learners to understand, especially at lower proficiency levels [Gilmore, 2007:105]. Teachers need to carefully select and adapt materials, provide explanations or scaffolding, and guide students through challenging content to ensure that learning remains effective and accessible.

Despite these challenges, the benefits of using realia and authentic materials outweigh the difficulties, as they provide a rich, contextualized, and culturally informed learning experience for students.

Conclusion. The use of realia in vocabulary teaching has been widely acknowledged by scholars. Schmitt emphasizes that learners retain vocabulary more effectively when they engage with meaningful input and contextualized examples rather than memorizing isolated word lists [Schmitt, 2000:7,9]. Gilmore highlights that authentic materials allow learners to experience natural language use while also introducing cultural elements, making lessons more relevant and engaging [Gilmore, 2007:100,106].

For Uzbek EFL students, realia provides a practical way to teach vocabulary by connecting new words with everyday life and familiar cultural contexts. Teachers can use objects such as food packages, classroom tools, clothing, or traditional items to illustrate vocabulary. Activities like handling objects or discussing their uses help students actively participate and understand new words in meaningful contexts. The use of realia makes vocabulary learning more interactive and effective. It can increase learners' motivation, engagement, and ability to use language in real communication while also supporting cultural awareness.

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